

Is Fermat's Least Time Principle Equivalent to a Least Information Approach?

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Fermat's Least Time Principle clearly refers to a path in space which is associated with the least time of travel. In particular, one could apply this approach to derive Snell's law, assuming a fixed initial $(x_0=0, y_0)$, change in index of refraction below $y=0$ and a fixed end point $(x_0=L, -y_0)$. Officially, the integral which is minimized is: $\int ds/v$ (1) where ds is a unit length on the curve traversed and v , the velocity.

In this note, we point out that $dt= ds/v$ is sometimes used in the literature as being proportional to the probability for a particle to be found in ds (see (2)). If a particle is moving fast, then dt is small and there is less probability of finding the particle (hence less information) than if it moves slowly. We argue that one may consider that Fermat's Least Time Principle is equivalent to a minimization of information. This suggests the notion of probability instead of deterministic physics which might at first be implied by the notion of minimal time.

This interpretation of information or least time may be fine for the derivation of the 2-D Snell's law, but fails in the analysis of 1-D reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 interface. This suggests that something more may be occurring. The notion of dt representing the probability for a detection-measurement hit is based on the idea of an interaction occurring at the center-of-mass point of the particle. Given the photon example, and $E=pc$, we suggest that there might be a different interpretation of information. For fixed E , if $c_1=c/2$, then $p_1=2p$. By taking $1/p_1$, one obtains the factor $1/2$ again. Thus, one might be able to consider $1/p$ as linked with information. Formally, $t=\text{distance}/c = p \cdot \text{distance}$ for light, but we suggest using this in general for both light and particles with rest mass. Then, $1/p$ is linked with information. High p means low $1/p$ and high information. One wishes to minimize information. A function which enforces the $1/p$ resolution is $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ like $dt=\text{constant}$.

This would explain the 2-D Snell's law Fermat's Least Time Principle case, but it also has implications for $p = m_0 v = (2m_0) (v/2)$. In this case, the particles have the same momentum, but different speeds. If one only thinks in terms of speed, then they carry different information, but in terms of an impulse hit, they carry the same information. If one insists that impulse hit is linked to information, then using $1/p$ as the information quantity seems to hold. As a result, one no longer follows the center-of-mass in space and time in such an approach. This suggests a different scheme which is ultimately equivalent to the statement that for $dt=\text{constant}$, $v=\text{constant}$, one has the same probability for each dx . Mathematically, $\exp(ipx)$ creates periodic regions proportional to $1/p$, but $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ yields a constant for each dx which is akin to $dt=\text{constant}$ in each of these dx regions.

The form $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to solve 1D reflection-refraction, while minimization of information px (part of the action $-Et+px$) allows one to find Snell's law.

Fermat's Least Time Principle

As indicated by the title, Fermat's Least Time Principle seems to be associated with choosing a trajectory in space which is linked to the least time of deterministic travel. In other words, it

seems one has a completely deterministic problem, but at the same time imposes a maximization process. As a well-known example, consider a photon starting at $(0, y_0)$ in a medium with index of refraction n_1 and moving towards an n_1 - n_2 interface at $y=0$ and then moving in the new n_2 medium to $x=L$ and $-y_0$. We use:

$$\text{Speed in medium 1} = c/n_1 \quad \text{speed in medium 2} = c/n_2 \quad \text{and } d=vt \quad ((1))$$

Then, we let x be the x point at the n_1 - n_2 interface at which the photon lands:

$$n_1/c \sqrt{x^2 + y_0^2} + n_2/c \sqrt{(L-x)^2 + y_0^2} \quad ((2))$$

Taking d/dx of ((2)) and setting this to 0 yields:

$$n_1 x / \sqrt{x^2 + y_0^2} - n_2 (L-x) / \sqrt{(L-x)^2 + y_0^2} = 0 \quad \text{or}$$

$$\sin(\theta_1) / \sin(\theta_2) = n_2/n_1 \quad ((3))$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 are measured from the y axis. ((3)) is Snell's Law.

In this calculation, there is no notion of a photon wavelength or quantum mechanics, one uses deterministic physics and index of refraction relations ((1)).

We argue, however, that matters are not as direct as they seem. If one considers one dimensional reflection-refraction, then one is immediately faced with a probability situation as a single photon may reflect or refract at an n_1 - n_2 interface. Furthermore, there is no opportunity to use Fermat's Least Time Principle in this case. In the 2-D Snell's Law case, one only considers refraction, but physically, reflection also occurs and this is linked with probability. As a result, we suggest that there is more involved with such a problem than simply thinking in terms of deterministic physics and minimizing time.

Minimal Information

In (2), it is argued that for a classical bound state, the time a particle spends in a fixed dx , i.e.

$$dt = dx/v(x) \quad \text{where } \frac{1}{2}mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

Is proportional to finding a particle in dx . If a particle moves very quickly, then dt is small and it is less likely to find the particle than if it moves slowly. This means that one has less information for a fast particle than a slow one, we argue. This view is associated with the probability of finding a particle in dx , even though ((4)) are completely deterministic equations.

We note that the notion of $dt = dx/v(x)$ is based on a constant $v(x)$ in dx , even though physically the particle accelerates. We have noted above that Fermat's Least Time Principle does not solve the 1-D reflection-refraction problem at an n_1 - n_2 junction. Is there a way to use

the notion of dt proportional to a probability to obtain a probabilistic theory which can solve the 1-D reflection-refraction problem?

If $v(x) = \text{constant}$, i.e. $V(x) = \text{constant}$, then dt is constant and one has the same probability for each fixed dx regardless of the value of v or $p = \text{momentum}$. In other words, dt is a relative probability which holds for a fixed v, p or for different v, p as in the 2-D Snell's law case where dt is used in both media. In the 1-D reflection-refraction case, this dt has no effect in solving the problem.

It seems that in both the 2-D and 1-D reflection-refraction cases, one must focus on an interaction which occurs at an n_1-n_2 junction. Minimal information through dt as a probability is used in the 2-D case, but something different must be used in the 1-D case, but it must consisten with the notion of $dt = \text{constant}$.

As a result, we suggest that the idea of information based on interactions with the center-of-mass of a particle (based solely on v) may be problematic. We wish to consider information in terms of interaction, in particular momentum based impulse hits.

Information In Terms of Momentum Based Impulse Hits

Fermat's Least Time Principle is successful for describing 2-D reflection and refraction, but fails in the 1-D case. We thus suggest that there must be more general ideas present. These ideas must describe the 1-D case, but then collapse to a theory which is consistent with the least time principle, i.e. dt proportional to probability scenario for the 2-D case.

In classical physics, an interaction occurs at the center-of-mass of a particle. $dt = dx/v(x)$ is linked to the center-of-mass motion and represents the amount of time (hence probability) of an interaction. A classical physical interaction, however, is based on an impulse hit proportional to the particle's momentum. In the Snell's law case, $E = pc$ and so for constant E ,

$1/p$ and c scale in the same manner ((5a))

Then, using $\text{distance}/c$ is equivalent to: $p * \text{distance}$ ((5b))

$P * \text{distance}$ is part of $-Et + px$ (with E constant) for the action, which then is also minimized.

One does not have to consider an interaction in terms of c/ni , but can think in terms of $1/p$.

We suggest that this is an interesting idea because if one has a classical particle with rest mass m_0 and v and another with $2m_0, .5v$, then the two have the same momentum impulse hit, but different speeds. According to the dt approach, they would have different probabilities for interaction, but according $1/p$, they would have the same. In a problem based on impulse hits, one would expect momentum to be the key variable and might consider

$1/p$ as linked to an interaction probability range due to $\text{distance} = 1/p$ yielding $p * 1/p = 1$ ((6))

This means that the $\text{constant}/p$ is the probability range and so for $2p$, one has twice the resolution. This resolution should be created by a periodic function in p, x , but one that is linked to the $dt = \text{constant}$ for a constant speed value of Fermat's Least Time Principle. This leads to:

$$\exp(ipx) \text{ such that } \exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1 \quad ((7))$$

High resolution or high p represents high information. Instead of minimizing time, one might minimize resolution which goes as $1/p$ which is the same as minimizing information. The benefit of this viewpoint is that one may use $\exp(ipx)$ to solve the 1-D reflection-refraction problem by considering:

$$A\exp(ip_1x) + B\exp(-ip_1x) = C\exp(ip_2x) \text{ where } p_1=p_{n1} \text{ and } p_2=p_{n2} \text{ and}$$

$$p_1A\exp(ip_1x) - p_1B\exp(-ip_1x) = p_2C\exp(ip_2x) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) requires considering reflection and refraction together. In 2-dimensions, one may consider each separately.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Fermat's Least Time Principle chooses a deterministic trajectory which minimizes time and is useful for solving both 2-D reflection and refraction trajectories. The problem is that it does not calculate the probabilities involved in 1-D reflection-refraction. In the 1D case one is forced to deal with reflection and refraction together and calculate their probabilities, whereas the trajectory is irrelevant. It seems that one should have a more complex theory than Fermat's Least Time Principle which is able to calculate probabilities in the 1-D reflection-refraction problem, but then also describe Snell's law in 2D.

We suggest that for $E=pc$ (light), $1/p$ scales as c and t scales as $1/c$ or as p . Instead of minimizing length/ c one may minimize p^* length. This leads to the notion of the minimization of an action for a free particle given by $-Et+px$, with px being part of this as E remains constant. We suggest that instead of considering interactions in time with the center-of-mass, one uses $1/p$ as a resolution measure as $px \rightarrow \Delta x = 1/p$. This leads to a function $\exp(ipx)$ which creates such a periodicity in space, but also yields $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) = 1$ just as $dt=\text{constant}$ for a constant v .

Minimizing time (distance/ c) in Fermat's Least Time Principle is the same as minimizing p^* distance. $1/p$ is resolution which is linked with information. The higher p , the more the information, thus it seems that one wishes to minimize information. This leads to an approach which solves both the 1D and 2D reflection-refraction problems.

References

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